

A Study on Impact of Team Work on Organizational Productivity with Special Referance at TVS Training and Service Pvt Ltd, Chennai

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ABSTRACT

Teamwork plays a vital part to make the performance of an organization competent and successful. Teamwork need participation of every single person who is a part of that specific team. Complete a good team is not an easy task. It require a lot of creative ability. And once a team is formed than it is necessary to guide your team mates and try to keep them together in order to achieve your specific target. Target can only be achieved from good team work. Which is not potential until and except there is a bonding in the team mates and they don't realize their duties deferential to their work. Best team work can be complete and it has reached to the final stage of the achievement of goal it is the example of best is not an easy task. Once a team is formed and it has reached to the finishing stage of the achievement of goal it is the example of best team work. Because getting to the final goal can be done with a good team work.

KEYWORDS: *teamwork, productivity, impact of teamwork, study on teamwork*

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INTRODUCTION

A team can be defined as a group of population with a full set of comes bonding skills needed to complete a task, job or project. Not only this, but there must be some common goal shared by teams and respective however there is a substantial difference between a group and a team. The main difference between a group and a team is the commonly of goals and objectives. A ream has some goals which are common by all of the organization members, but this is not always current in a group. Teamwork is defined as a process which involves participation of a group of people in order to achieve a goal. It is basically the capability to work peaceful for a common purpose. Teams give the advantage to work more professionally as a participation effort in order to achieve the goal. Teamwork provides range of ideas during the time of decision making as every team members participate and offers his/her idea with a different frame of associating. Teamwork offers a team members as well as the estimation of the task and performance.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

To understand the importance of working as team and impact of team courage on achieving organization goals.
To complement participate skill when prepare teamwork concepts.

To be able to use techniques for handling team mutual problems.

To gain larger insight into:

- -why teams succeed and fail
- -team norms, role and stages.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

Research design is an arrangement of condition for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to integrate relevance to the research purpose with the economy in procedure. The research should specific the approach with respect to the proposed study.

DESCRIPTIVE RESEACH DESIGN:

The research has used descriptive research for the study. Describe research focuses on the characteristics of a group or a situation.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Data source : primary data
Research type : Survey
Research approach : Questionnaire
Sampling plan : Purposive sampling until
Contact method : Personal interview.

Research tools:

In the study the primary data was collected through questionnaires from respondents directly. A questionnaire contain list of questions relating to certain specific, which the research collects the data.

The research has set up different question like close-end open-end and separation questions using both nominal and ordinal scaling.

Types other questions

Close-end questions

Examples:

- Organization
- Employee
- Both
- Open-end questions

SAMPLING METHOD:

Sampling random:

In random sampling each members of the population has a known and equal adjustment if being selected.

Sampling technique:

The approach is calculate sampling technique, where some restriction are put on the possible admittance of a number in a sample, it is purposive.

Sample size:

The survey was finish by a sample size 100 respondents. Samples are collected in TVS training and service pvt ltd Chennai.

Sampling unit:

The sample was collected from the employees TVS pvt ltd in Chennai.

Data collection method:

Data are assemble from both primary & secondary sources. Primary data collected through structured questionnaire and secondary data are assemble from official website of the company, journals, articles, textbooks, etc..

PRIMARY DATA:

Most important data are believed as the first hand information collected from the people who responded. The most important data is collected by structured questionnaires.

SECONDARY DATA:

The secondary data are collected from the books, magazines and internet.

Title of the research:

The selected title of the study deal as "A STUDY ON IMPACT OF TEAM WORK ON ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY WITH SPECIAL REFERANCE AT TVS TRAINING AND SERVICE PVT LTD, CHENNAI.

Area of research:

The study is conducted in Chennai city.

Period of research:

The data collected in the date of 24/02/2020 to 03/03/2020.

Questionnaires Design:

Questionnaires contains demographical and socio economic profile of the respondents, various attributes & factors related to product awareness is used in the questionnaire, some open ended, close ended & rating questions were used to know awareness level of consumers.

Tools used for analysis:

This part of study is mainly focused on verifying main objective of the study. Research used SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS using charts and tables, CHI SQUARE, CORRELATION and ONE WAY ANOVA as statistical tool for analysis of data.

1. CHI SEUQARE TEST:

Hypothesis:

Relationship between the gender and back-up when your current employees leaves the organization.

Null hypothesis:

There is no relationship between age and the gender respondent's perception towards to enhance 'team work on organizational productivity'

Calculate value of

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (c-1) * (r-1)$$

$$= (5-1) * (2-1)$$

$$= 4$$

4 at 5% level of significance.

$$C.V < T.V$$

Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted,

Alternative hypothesis is rejected.

RESULT:

There is no significant relationship between the gender and satisfaction current job.

2. ANOVA

Hypothesis:

Null hypothesis:

There is significant ANOVA between the gender and back-up plan when a current employees leaves the organization.

CONCLUTION:

Calculated F value is 636.643 and F critical value 3.888 so calculated value is more than the table value so null is rejected.

E. CORRELATION:

Calculation value is 0.124 and so I concluded that there is no significant correlation between rate statement and teamwork should be progress of the company.

FINDINGS:

- 69% of respondents belongs to the male class.
- 71% of the respondents are married.
- 48% of the respondents are in the age of 21-35 yrs.
- 68% of the respondents are Diploma holders.
- 67% of the respondents are urban areas.
- 45% of the respondents are below 15,000 income category.
- 43% of the respondents are agree the accountable for the decision they make.
- 58% of the respondents are agree the work assigned is distributed fairly.

- 47% of the respondents are agree the communication within the team is transparent.
- 36% of the respondents are agree the sufficient is made to get the opinion and ideas of the employees.
- 38% of the respondents are agree the spirit of teamwork within company.
- 34% of the respondents are neutral the team members assume leadership role and proactively.
- 37% of the respondents are agree the team members work systematically to complete tasks.
- 44% of the respondents are agree the members are careful as to not to hurt others feeling.
- 37% of the respondents are agree the team members clearly understand their role.
- 40% of the respondents are strongly agree the team members appreciate one another's unique capabilities.
- 38% of the respondents are agree the team members are effective listeners.
- 37% of the respondents are neutral are team members maintain a can do approach when they encounter frustrating situation.
- 39% of the respondents are agree the trust exists among team members.
- 41% of the respondents are neutral the team members are prepared to engage in debate around ideas.
- 39% of the respondents are neutral the team members are viewed as unique people.
- 40% of the respondents are neutral the team members are prepared to check among themselves to assure progress and overcome obstacles to progress.
- 41% of the respondents are strongly agree the vision and mission of the team are accepted by all the team members.
- 38% of the respondents are neutral the effective teamwork is facilitated by clear and open communication.
- 39% of the respondents are very quickly the politely do members of your team treat each other's.
- 45% of the respondents are very quickly the team adjust to changing.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Don't overdo it on the number of tasks, combine smaller task using the task description feature.
- Create a standardized reference system to keep the task lists templates organized.
- Keep messaging concise and actionable.
- Leave in-depth discussion for other tools.
- All employees should be clear on the long-term goals of the organization.
- This should be covered during the onboarding process for new employees and regular updates should be made company meeting.
- One of the best ways to build camaraderie in the workplace is to give formal recognition for the best things to praise your employees for is excellent teamwork.
- Showing gratitude for altruistic behavior is an excellent way to create an awesome, friendly culture. When you

have a workplace when people are reward for helping one another, teamwork will naturally improve.

Conclusion:

The research shows a strong conclusive significant relationship between the self-reliant variables namely teamwork, esprit de corps, team confidence, acceptance & rewards and employee performance. However, teamwork was highly correlated with employee performance. The overall results uncover that teamwork which brings reward in teams of higher productivity, better organizational performance, aggressive advantage and increased product quantity highly benefaction to organizational productivity compared to other factors.

Employers may be able to improve their performance by increasing the volume of teamwork and taking action to raise the performance level of the individual, but to succeed in this they need to pay attention to the quantity and type of teamwork offered. Teamwork activity within the organization is very much beneficial and its effect is directly on employee performance. When an employee acquires adequate opportunities of teamwork his/her performance automatically improves and he/she will be satisfied with the job and this could ensure that skills are better utilized. This might decrease the possibility of an employee quittings a job.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alie, R. E., Beam, H., and Carey, T. A. (1998). The use of teams in an undergraduate management program. *Journal of Management Education*, 22(6), 707-19.
- [2] Anderson, N., and West, M. (2002). The personality of team working. *Journal of Personal Management*, 4(3), 81.
- [3] Bacon, N., and Blyton, P. (2006). Union co-operation in a context of job insecurity: Negotiated outcomes from team working. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 44(2), 215-23.
- [4] Boyt, T., Lusch, R., and Mejza, M. (2005). Theoretical Model of the Antecedents and consequences of organizational, workgroup and Professional esprit de Corps. *European Management Journal*, 23(6), 682-701.
- [5] Boyt, T., Lusch, R. F., and Naylor, G. (2001). The Role of Professionalism in Determining Job Satisfaction in Professional Services: A Study of Marketing Researchers. *Journal of Service Research*, 3(4), 321-330.
- [6] Cohen, S. G., and Bailey, D. E. (1999). What makes teams work: group effectiveness research from the shop floor to the executive suite? *Journal of Management*, 23(3), 239-90.
- [7] Conti, B., and Kleiner, B. (2003). How to increase teamwork in Organizations. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Education*, 14(3), 243-250. , 5(1), 26-29.